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WP4: Transformation

Short Report of the Cross-Sectoral Working Roundtable

By Kirsty Blackstock¹, Anna Bérczi-Siket, Fanni Nyíró, Alhassan Ibrahim, Melinda Aitner-Óváry, Kerry Waylen, Esther Carmen, Daniel Hering, Sebastian Birk, Rebecca Gray.

The H2020 MERLIN roundtables aim to build communities of practice linking economic sector, policy and civil society representatives supported by MERLIN scientific and implementation partners. This report captures the main discussion points of the Cross-sectoral working roundtable. The findings will shape the proposed European Routemap due later in 2025.

Summary

- Over 40 participants gathered to discuss cross-sectoral working to mainstream taking a Nature-based Solutions (NbS) approach to freshwater restoration. See pages 1-3.
- Different points of view were provided from policy, science and advocacy networks, which illustrated the need for, and benefits from, working across different economic sectors. See pages 3-4.
- Examples of cross-sectoral working from North-East France and Romania were provided. See page 4.
- Participants in break out rooms discussed how sectors might implement, affect or be affected by four types of restoration measures – land use change, floodplain reconnection, peatland restoration and removal or bypassing transversal barriers.
 - Our initial analysis had identified most of the sectors involved, but some missing sectors were highlighted. The discussion added useful detail, examples and drew attention to the importance of context. See pages 5-10.
- Participants then discussed four actions that may support cross-sectoral working, namely policy changes, funding and finance, knowledge sharing and partnerships.
 - The discussions again added useful detail, examples and drew attention to the importance of working across silos (between policies, between types of funding, sharing knowledge and having a mediating organisation to coordinate sectors). See pages 10-13.
- The report was open for comments from participants until 21st March 2025 and then finalised. One participant responded *“I agree with the focus, and while agriculture is likely the main sector of emphasis, all sectors play a crucial role in landscape restoration and must be addressed together in an integrated approach. This is an important message for policymakers to consider.”*

Purpose of the Roundtable

The H2020 MERLIN project (Mainstreaming Ecological Restoration of freshwater-related ecosystems in a Landscape context: INnovation, upscaling and transformation) aims for transformative ecosystem restoration, mainstreaming Nature-based Solutions (NbS) for urgent systemic change.

A key part of the NbS approach is to involve multiple different stakeholders with expertise and knowledge about freshwater ecosystems, and how they are used. As part of developing a cross-sectoral routemap for Europe, we met with 41 stakeholders on 6th February to discuss how different economic sectors were involved in landscape level NbS to restore freshwater ecosystems.

What is a routemap? Who is it for?

¹ For more information, please contact Kirsty.Blackstock@hutton.ac.uk

A routemap is the provision of a range of options to reach a certain destination. In our case, we propose a [vision](#) whereby:

- taking a NbS approach to freshwater restoration is in all relevant sectors’ toolbox by 2030,
- by 2040 freshwater NbS are being upscaled as part of sectoral business models and
- by 2050, freshwater NbS are being mainstreamed throughout Europe.

We recognise that our starting points are an ongoing implementation of the EU integration principle, integrative policy drivers like the Green Deal, and risks to business and society through climate and biodiversity crises. This can be combined with business opportunities arising from restoration, such as fishing and eco-tourism revenues stemming from riparian woodlands or wetlands. The routemap will focus on [selected restoration measures](#) and the [actions](#) that support cross-sectoral working to implement and mainstream these measures. This creates a decision space for all those involved in strategic governance of freshwater ecosystems.

We aim to [add value to the existing guidance](#) on NbS across multiple settings and to the existing guidance on freshwater restoration. Our focus is taking a NbS approach to freshwater restoration in rural areas. The routemap is therefore for all relevant stakeholder organisations making strategic decisions about freshwater ecosystems, including private, non-governmental and public organisations. These stakeholders might be working at the European, transboundary, member state or sub-regional levels. Due to the focus on transformation, the main users of the routemap are likely to be ‘change agents’ seeking to go beyond the status quo to achieve the vision at scale and at pace.

Why cross-sectoral working?

A sector is a collection of economic or business interests - in the H2020 MERLIN project we have worked with six economic sectors (agriculture, hydropower, insurance, navigation, peat extraction and water supply and sanitation), building informal communities of practice to share knowledge and good practice regarding how sectors can support, and benefit from, freshwater restoration (see [here](#) for more information).

Learning from the strategic European scale, and listening to our 18 local [Case studies](#), suggests it is vital to understand how different sectors interact within a catchment or landscape. Understanding and enabling integrative resource management requires identifying all the relevant sectors involved in freshwater restoration, including those involved in implementing measures and those affected by the measures. In addition to the six sectors above, we have identified other sectors including: forestry, fisheries, eco-tourism, sand and gravel mining, urban development, banking and finance and conservation.

Understanding how the costs and benefits of freshwater restoration are shared, including how to mitigate trade-offs and maximise synergies through collaboration and coordination, is essential. Therefore, cross-sectoral working means identifying the main actions required to manage trade-offs and the distribution of outcomes.

What happened at the Roundtable?

The Cross-sectoral working Roundtable was held on 6th February 2025 and brought together 41 experts online for three hours. The participant organisations are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Participants attending the Cross-sectoral Roundtable

Organisation	Number	Organisation	Number
DG Agriculture	3	Responsibly Produced Peat	1
DG Budget	1	DG JRC (Joint Research Centre)	1
DG Clima	1	Total Non-Merlin Participants	21

DG Env	2	Bundesanstalt für Gewässerkunde (Federal Institute for Hydrology)	2
European Angling Association	1	Deltares	1
European Centre for River Restoration	1	Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research (UFZ)	1
European Environment Agency	3	I-Catalist	1
European Investment Bank	1	International Peat Society	3
German Directorate-General for Waterways and Shipping	1	James Hutton Institute	5
Institute for European Environmental Policy	1	National Institute for Research and Development on Marine Geology and Geoecology	1
International Network of Basin Organisations	1	University of Duisberg-Essen	2
Latvian National Peatland Society	1	WWF - CEE	4
Network Nature	1	Total MERLIN participants	20**
European Research Executive Agency	1	** 11 were moderators or note takers	

The roundtable had a brief icebreaker exercise, where we established the geographical and sectoral spread of the participants. An overview of the project and the focus of the routemap was presented and then there were five invited speakers who gave complementary ‘points of view’ about the need for cross-sectoral working to deliver transformative NbS. The main points made were:

- Christine Falter from [DG Agri](#) emphasized the importance of cross-sectoral collaboration through two examples of projects funded under the Common Agricultural Policy. The first example from Spain highlights Water Framework Directive related payments, where farmers in the Aragon region are incentivized to cultivate flood-tolerant crops in the Ebro River floodplain. Effective cooperation between water authorities and agricultural policy bodies was crucial, especially at the planning stage. The second example from Austria focuses on high-nature-value farmland, where farmers collaborate with nature conservation authorities to develop regional protection plans. They receive tailored advice and financial support to adopt sustainable practices. Falter stressed the need for a facilitating body to coordinate such efforts and ensure the right incentives, such as public or private funding, for ecosystem service provision.
- Evelyn Underwood from [IEEP](#) and [Network Nature](#) noted the context in which the Nature Restoration Law requires the Member States (MS) to produce national restoration plans (NRPs) and start reporting in 2028, which is a unique opportunity to explain the benefits of restoration to economic sectors. NRPs will require integration with other policies as well as information and capacity building to target restoration in the most effective locations (see article 4 of the Nature Restoration Law (NRL)).
- Daniel Hering, coordinator of [H2020 MERLIN](#) discussed the role of science in mainstreaming ecosystem restoration, particularly for freshwater systems, and fostering cross-sectoral cooperation. He highlighted key scientific contributions of MERLIN, including monitoring, developing NbS, and co-creating sectoral transformation pathways. MERLIN has also played a crucial role in informing policy, with contributions to the NRL through policy briefs and advocacy efforts. Hering emphasized the need for coherent implementation connecting the Common

Agricultural Policy (CAP) and the NRL's implementation, exploring new financing mechanisms, including private sector involvement, and aligning economic sector interests with restoration goals under the regulatory framework.

- Albert Scrieci from [GeoEcoMar](#) presented two freshwater-related projects that they carried out. First, he talked about the challenges facing the Lower Danube River, such as declining water levels, pollution, bank erosion, and desertification. In the REXUS project, they examined the competing demands of the hydropower, navigation, agriculture and water supply and sanitation sectors, where irrigation needs often conflict with energy production, sediment transport and drinking water provision, particularly during low-water periods. To address these challenges, the project explored strategies for optimal water allocation. Another project Scrieci introduced was the Carasuhat Wetland restoration, led by WWF Romania, which re-established natural hydrological conditions. The project demonstrated how NbS can mitigate flood risks, support biodiversity, and create economic opportunities through ecotourism and sustainable fisheries.
- Franck Perru, from the Syndicat des Eaux et de l'Assainissement Alsace-Moselle ([SDEA](#)) provided a short video on managing nature with NbS. Through their partnerships with local farmers, SDEA (water authority) has been working for over 20 years to address challenges such as heavy rainfall and the management of water flow from agricultural lands and villages. For example, they've implemented NbS, such as installing hedges to prevent soil erosion, adapting crops to better align with seasonal rainfall patterns, and modifying river courses to improve water retention and prevent flooding. These efforts have not only protected villages from mudslides but also helped maintain biodiversity, enhance soil quality, and create more resilient agricultural practices.

Further information was provided by the organisers about the specific areas of content where the participants' expertise was being sought. These revolved around four different freshwater restoration measures (land use change, floodplain reconnection, wetland restoration, barrier removal or bypass) and four different actions (policy, funding and financing, knowledge sharing and partnership working) to encourage cross-sectoral working.

Then the participants broke into separate breakout groups to discuss one measure and one action. Note that some participants left at this stage. Each group was supported by a moderator and a notetaker. An online whiteboard (MIRO) was provided for each exercise, to enable individuals to give written comments and redraw the diagrams, as well as holding a more conventional online discussion. There were a variety of approaches to using these resources, from little use of the whiteboard to a collective redrawing of the diagrams.

The meeting and breakout groups were recorded and transcripts produced using Artificial Intelligence associated with the Microsoft Word software. These transcripts, recordings and the notes were used to produce this report. Ethical clearance was obtained from the James Hutton Institute Ethics Committee, and the participants were sent information sheets including the informed consent principles before the meeting. The meeting began with an opportunity to raise questions about the purpose of the meeting and their consent to participate and if participants stayed in the meeting, they were deemed to have consented. Participants were invited to check and correct a draft version of this report.

Cross-sectoral involvement in Restoration Measures

The participants were introduced to four generic restoration measures:

- Land Use Change (9 participants)
- Floodplain reconnection (7 participants)
- Peatland and Wetland restoration (9 participants)
- Transversal Barrier Removal (8 participants)

The primary emphasis was on determining [who should be involved](#) in implementing the measures rather than debating the measures themselves.

Land Use Change

The examples of land use change discussed included extensification, seasonal grazing, planting water tolerant perennial crops, organic farming for cleaner water supply, paludiculture for biomass. MERLIN case studies demonstrate good examples for land use change. Implementation of land use change creates opportunities as it may increase resilience to droughts, reduce sediments and pollutants, and increase biodiversity. However, these changes (extensification, changing farming or forestry systems, swapping from chemical weedkillers to a more biodiverse approach to ground management under powerlines) may incur costs such as new machinery or reduce the yields, loss of CAP subsidies or overall profit per hectare.

An example was provided from Hungary, where agriculture is the biggest land user, and due to its geography, the water management system is developed to drain water from the fields into the rivers. Agriculture subsidies and high need for crops led to intensive farming systems on the plain areas. Environmental and biodiversity impacts of intensive farming, soil loss, such as loss of habitats, invasive species and lack or variable precipitation distribution led to semi desert status between the Danube and the Tisza rivers (called Sand Ridge/Homokhátság). Cooperation among sectors (agriculture, water operation company, public sector) is required to reach a solution that keeps water on the land to avoid drought, and water restoration NbS could be a catalyst. A key question is to find economic incentives for farmers and landowners to change land use to floodplain farming methods. Good practices are very important but are too small scale. A diverse, mosaic like landscape management is not an economic alternative for farmers. This short film (with English subtitles) gives a good summary.

In terms of sectoral influence on land use change, there was discussion about the differences between urban and rural land use change - with rural areas perceived to have fewer stakeholders managing more land, but with more power and influence. Some may dislike external interventions into how they manage their land. Where there is competition for high quality agricultural land (e.g. in Flanders) then it is harder to achieve land use change e.g. away from growing potatoes on riparian land. Insurance companies sometimes buy land as investment and therefore are not willing to allow restoration if this impairs the purpose for which they invested. A participant commented on the report that to address challenges associated with land use and restoration, catchments should be mapped and evaluated for their priority and potential for restoration contributions, including further co-benefits such as water purification and mitigation of floods and droughts.

Figure 1: Land Use MIRO board at the end of the breakout group

However, there are also potential win-wins involving insurance, as often companies may not provide a flood or drought risk insurance product if the farmers do not adopt climate friendly practices or change their land use. Another win-win identified was eco-tourism, which can provide diversification opportunities to farmers and provide new jobs in the rural economy. Spatial planning actors in the public and different NGOs can provide a useful integrative and coordination role and help ensure conservation is considered alongside other sectors (e.g. agriculture, manufacturing, tourism).

Potentially **missing sectors** were identified as the health sector and the government sector, particularly spatial planning. It is important to make 'room for the river' so that if other sectors agree to e.g. reconnect floodplains and remove barriers (see sections below) there is space for natural hydrological processes to occur.

Floodplain Reconnection

The group discussed floodplain restoration in the context of improving longitudinal, lateral and transversal **connectivity**, over time. It is important to consider all types of water bodies, including both small streams and large rivers. It may be necessary to focus on (re)creating multiple streams, not just reconnecting floodplains if the river channels have already been transformed (e.g. heavily incised).

Figure 2: Floodplain reconnection MIRO board at the end of the break out group

This group worked on the MIRO board for some time before discussing the diagram - the results of this brainstorming are presented in Figure 2. In general there was strong agreement over where sectors were affected by the measure. There are some examples of the navigation sector working with conservation in the US and Spain. Agriculture was deemed to be the sector most likely to be affected by the benefits from reconnection in terms of reduction in flooding, and potential for more resilience against drought, particularly if the measure helps maintain groundwater used for irrigation. Focussing on the **benefits to the sectors**, including potential economic development opportunities e.g. aquaculture, as a form of diversification from high yield agriculture. However, there was disagreement regarding hydropower, as some participants felt that floodplain reconnection could affect sedimentation, which has an impact on

hydropower barriers. Many sectors could be affected by aging infrastructure, whereby NbS could be more cost-effective than sustaining grey infrastructure that separates the channel from the floodplain. It was also important to allay fears about perceived risks from reconnecting floodplains, e.g. Water Supply operators worrying that water quality may be affected.

No **missing sectors** were identified but our notes pick up that forestry and aquaculture were mentioned and could be added. Some sectors can be both ‘above’ and ‘below’ in the diagram – they are both affected by, and help to deliver, restoration. Examples of these include Agriculture, Water Supply and, potentially, Insurance. Different types of organisations were discussed, with large projects tending to be led by State public authorities, and smaller pilots led by NGOs. It is important to motivate collaboration but to also target who should be involved, as involving ‘everyone in everything’ will be overwhelming and counterproductive.

Peatland and Wetland Restoration

Firstly, there was a discussion about whether both terms were needed, given that peatlands are a form of wetlands. However, the discussion appears to have used the term peatlands throughout as there are particular policy and land use implications for peatlands. There was also a discussion about whether restoration meant rewetting or revegetation, and the group agreed that both approaches should be considered and the most appropriate should be selected depending on the site conditions. **Context**, both the biophysical conditions and the socio-economic and policy conditions, were important in all the breakout groups but were particularly stressed in this group, as land ownership models have a big effect on how restoration decisions are made (for example between private ownership in Scandinavia and public ownership in some Baltic states). The focus on peatlands varies by region: for instance, they are a focal point in the Baltic but less so in Denmark due to historical drainage for agriculture.

Landowners tend to be agriculture and forestry or public authorities managing for conservation objectives. **Many sectors** can be directly or indirectly involved, including tourism, recreation (hunting, birdwatching, some fishery), science, conservation, peat extraction companies; and any changes to the water table should involve the local water authorities and Water supply and sanitation (WSS) sector. Reduction in flood risk or drought through rewetting upland peatlands and wetlands could be relevant to the insurance sector. Energy companies could be involved where there are cases of combining paludiculture with solar panel farms, but overall bioenergy was not seen as significant. In some Member States (MS), e.g. Germany, peat extraction companies can restore alongside extraction but in most cases, the restoration occurs as ‘after-use’ once the peat extraction company has finished. The construction sector is involved through their role in blocking drains etc; and in some settings the ‘carbon market’ (e.g. finance) is an important sector. As with the land use change group, the participants identified the importance of local authorities and national park authorities in coordinating these multiple sectors to take a landscape level approach, particularly where peatland restoration takes place in upland areas. There was further consideration of the roles of those responsible for direct intervention versus those who incentivize change. These discussions led to a revised diagram shown in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Revised diagram of Sectors involved in peatland (wetland) restoration

Transversal Barrier Removal

This group spent quite a bit of time discussing river **connectivity** – the main focus here is longitudinal connectivity but other measures, e.g. flood plain connection is about lateral connectivity. A third type of connectivity is vertical connectivity (note: see EU Biodiversity strategy barrier removal guidance). The group agreed that the focus should be appropriate removal of instream transversal barriers, especially those not in active use, recognising the strategic importance of hydropower barriers (and other barriers necessary for water storage or navigation). Nuance is important as barriers vary (e.g. in their capacity to store water) and thus their influence on water scarcity and flooding is contextually determined. The measure does not include out-of-channel reservoirs.

Following on from this was a discussion of the ecological **benefits** of restoring connectivity, and the urgent need to reverse the decline in freshwater fauna. An example from a Spanish LIFE project was given of a small barrier that was removed providing flood protection benefits and the resulting changes in the hydrology were seen to help improve aquifer recharge in an over exploited (water scarce) area, whereas in other cases barriers hold water upstream, which can also encourage groundwater recharge. Climate adaptation strategies of sectors may see obsolete barriers being used again, e.g. for irrigation. There can be strong cultural attachment to barriers, opposition to the use of public funding and fears about negative consequences of barrier removal, as illustrated by a case in Germany. There were also discussions about other associated aspects of flood risk and drought management, as well as the importance of managing non-native invasive species.

Figure 4: Barrier Removal MIRO board at the end of the break out group

The sectors involved in this measure are shown in Figure 4. Further comments on the sectors involved included the need to include ecotourism and interactions with recreational and commercial fishery. The fishery sector can implement barrier removal and benefit from these measures. There is also a blurred boundary between life insurance sector and the wider banking or finance sector, which are relevant sectors for financing measures, including providing social benefits that can be important for local pension providers. Insurance was identified as a potential partner to fund the implementation of the measure, as they could benefit from it as well. Whilst the insurance sector is increasingly interested in adaptation to climate change, it is still unclear how to get the sector to invest. Finally, freshwater aquaculture was identified as a **missing sector**, as their installations can block/reduce fish migration and abstract river water.

Actions to encourage cross-sectoral working

The participants were introduced to four generic actions to encourage cross-sectoral working. Each breakout room discussed one action:

- Policy drivers (including potential policy changes) (9 participants)
- Funding and Finance (7 participants)
- Knowledge sharing (9 participants)
- Partnership working (8 participants)

Where relevant topics were raised in another breakout room or during a discussion of the measures, the material has been consolidated under the relevant heading below. However, compared to the information about cross-sectoral involvement in measures, there was less discussion.

Policy Opportunities

The main focus was on [strategic plans](#), implemented by the Member States (MS). River Basin Management Plans (RBMPs) could provide a coordinating platform for cross-sectoral working including NGO and scientific expertise, but do not always work like this. Forthcoming National Nature Restoration Plans will be considered in the 4th round of RBMPs from 2027 onwards. The Commission can recommend more inclusive participation and integration of different sectoral plans, but the action needs to be implemented by the individual MS. A good summary of policies related to land use change and NbS can be found [here](#).

CAP agri-environmental measures are also available for supporting NbS implementation, but the level of support is still low. Agreements under these schemes last 5 years, and there is a risk that after this period farmers change their farming method to a more profitable intensive land use. Other state-led interventions include [land reallocation schemes](#) that buy farms from retiring farmers without successors and reallocates them to active farmers, including designating parcels for land use change and restoration as part of the process – an example was given from the Netherlands that has been running for over 40 years, and is financed in part by the Oil and Gas Sector. The need for land swapping arrangements was also raised in the peatland restoration breakout group; this could involve mechanisms such as land purchases elsewhere, land swap systems, land banks, or other land compensation arrangements.

Currently, some MS (e.g. in the Netherlands and in Hungary) pay compensation to farmers after extreme floods or droughts, which [undermines incentives to change](#) land use to be more resilient to climate change (raised in the land use change breakout). This is an area that could be revised to allow incentives from disaster-risk insurance to become more important in land use decision-making. Furthermore, the breakout group believed that land use change, rather than short-term (seasonal) flooding of land in winter, was more sustainable.

During the floodplain reconnection breakout discussion, the need for policy integration was highlighted, those implementing the CAP should become involved in the production of National Restoration Plans. This requires not only cross-references in documents, but active involvement in making the plans and sharing good practice. [Policy integration](#) was also highlighted in the peatland restoration breakout group, where meeting the NRL targets for peatlands requires thinking about integration with Water Framework Directive, Marine Strategy Framework Directive, Floods Directive, Habitats Directive Prioritised Action Framework, CAP and the Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry policy are all important. In some MS, like Germany, meeting the climate mitigation targets from the land use sector may require more peatland restoration than currently addressed in the NRL.

During the barrier removal breakout group, there were references to whether the NRL has changed the decision-making around when and how to remove barriers. The technical guidance (currently being updated) explains the definition of free-flowing stretches and whether barrier removal will contribute to the overall NRL target. The proposed [Water Resilience Strategy](#) was seen as an important driver for connectivity, and this was out for consultation during the roundtable. This provides a more precise focus for the wider policy domain of Climate Adaptation. Finally, the group was reminded of the importance of MS consenting conditions, where hydropower companies in Sweden were “obliged to release a certain number of reared fish to the river annually. This decision is an attempt to maintain a sufficient population size for commercial and recreational fishing” (quote extracted from the chat).

Funding and Finance

The breakout group noted that we should always expect the [public sector](#) to be involved in funding NbS, but perhaps the European Investment Bank and other banks can play more of a role in future in providing finance for big projects. Corporations who have objectives for water neutrality or carbon neutrality (e.g. Coca Cola, Intel) could be interested in funding floodplain restoration projects. To attract [private finance](#), the potential benefits of these NbS measures need to be specified in a quantitative way, and need monitoring, verification and reporting to build financiers’ confidence that objectives are being delivered. Standardisation of measures and monitoring can assist with such processes and help communicate with new financiers and funders.

The group also highlighted the need to fund transitions to adapted agriculture, e.g. extensive grazing, wet farming. The [CAP payments](#) were seen as most appropriate for this purpose. Here we can add the need to remove inappropriate incentives, such as those mentioned in the land use change breakout, whereby some MS provide relief payments for floods and droughts, which disincentivise adapting farm business models to allow flood plains to fulfill their natural functions.

The peatland restoration group also highlighted the importance of **compensation for land use changes** created by peatland restoration. This was elaborated upon, as there could be compensation or alternative business opportunities through managing wetlands (e.g. tourism or paludiculture). However, it can be difficult to substitute high returns from intensive farming on lowland peat soils with these more extensive farming and farm diversification models (e.g. in Germany). Furthermore, managing peatlands also requires funding, as often there are requirements for seasonal pumping and construction of wetland areas.

The barrier removal breakout also highlighted the need to establish how to fund or finance the measure. Some participants believed the best way to fund measures was through **taxing water users** (following cost-recovery principles in WFD (Article 9), although this language was not used). Other participants identified the potential for the insurance sector to fund such measures, although the discussion implied that this would be via life insurance long term investments rather than risk reduction annual insurance.

Knowledge Sharing

The peatland restoration breakout group linked knowledge sharing to the other issues discussed in the section on restoration above, as all aspects required **building shared understanding** and exchanging information on best practice. For example, when rewetting is sufficient to allow restoration and when revegetation might be required, or under which conditions peat extraction companies might become involved in wider landscape restoration projects (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Peatland Restoration MIRO board on Knowledge Sharing

During the floodplain reconnection discussions, the group agreed with the need to collect and share **success stories** – the group agreed that we all know examples of 1) making changes that deliver benefits on ground, 2) sectoral involvement in funding/delivering floodplain connection, 3) multi-sector involvement for floodplain connection (though this 3rd type is the rarest). Sharing such success stories with potential financiers such as large corporations may also unlock finance. To encourage cross-sectoral working to support floodplain reconnection, it was seen as essential to highlight the benefits, including both the ‘core benefit’ e.g. flood risk reduction and wider ‘co-benefits’ such as improved water resilience through groundwater recharge. Anticipating perceptions of floodplain reconnection risks e.g. of reduced water quality was also considered as key. Conversely, explaining the risks from the status quo, where floodplains remain disconnected, is also important. Finally, the group noted the need for advice to help farmers move towards extensive grazing and wet farming on reconnected floodplains, so that more business opportunities can be developed with this new ‘eco-cultural’ use of floodplains.

The land use breakout group talked about the need for awareness raising and **knowledge sharing** by enthusiasts of restoration farming to convince and influence their peers. Transformative change will

require a shift from maximising yields to sustainable farming, as well as policy signals. [Tools](#) can also help, for example, in Hungary, the national water authority has recently launched an app where farmers can propose parts of their own lands as a restoration site to improve the water supply and soil health on the rest of their lands. Comments on the report highlighted two distinct roles for science, ecological expertise to help with catchment prioritisation processes and wider range of sciences related to technical implementation.

Partnership Working

Some participants felt that current governance arrangements for water are not ‘fit-for-purpose’ as they promote policy silos and don’t encourage collaboration or change. Therefore, we may need new institutional arrangements to foster more collaboration between sectors and associated government departments. Others felt that there was policy coherence at the level of the Commission Policy Units and policy development, and this has improved a lot in the previous decade. Therefore, it is important to recognise that policy incoherence or siloed governance is a problem of [policy implementation](#) within the MS (see also policy section above).

Here the need to work together was recognised and associated with learning and sharing good practice (see knowledge sharing). However, working together and sharing knowledge can be difficult due to [different MS regulatory contexts](#) that affect how measures are governed. Developing informal communities of practice, including through projects like MERLIN or LIFE projects can be useful ways to build partnerships, even for the duration of the project. During the floodplain reconnection break out group, they discussed the need for targeted collaboration as trying to involve all potential affected stakeholders can be too difficult. To understand how sectors might work together can require engaging with lobbyists, however it is important to understand the constraints on different organisations’ roles (e.g. PIANC are non-political and therefore need to be careful how they interact with interest groups.)

Furthermore, the barrier removal breakout group highlighted that partnership working can be driven by setting the right [institutional incentives](#) to overcome any conflicts of interests and provide a business case to support other sectors. Consent conditions for water use and infrastructure could be used to drive more collaboration (see also policy, funding and finance sections above). A concept called ‘SHARE’ was highlighted that can help with equitable distribution of benefits from multi-purpose dams but it is unclear if this could be adapted for governing barrier removal.

Property rights are important. The example of peatland restoration in Ireland was given, where progress can be made as the public sector has responsibility for restoring past peat extraction sites. In other settings, measures implemented in one site may affect land managers in the vicinity and this needs coordination to manage these types of trade-offs. In general, implementing measures where there are many private landowners makes life more complicated and often needs a [mediator](#) to coordinate these different individuals.

Next Steps

The data from the roundtable discussions will be combined with our initial analyses developed from a policy review, synthesis of the six sectoral strategies and information from the MERLIN case studies found in their implementation plans and regional scalability plans.

We are aiming for a [draft routemap](#) by the summer that we can use for further discussions with key representatives from sectoral and policy organisations. The final routemap should be available later in 2025.

Please let us know if there are [specific opportunities](#) where we can share information with you or anyone else who may find these insights relevant. We are very happy to have further bilateral discussions.

Acknowledgements:

Thank you to our participants for their insights and enthusiasm. In particular, thank you to [our invited speakers](#) for their animations before the break out group discussions.